

OVERALL PROGRESS

Genetic evaluation and utilization

BW 78 – a new variety for the low country wet zone

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The so-called “miracle rices” of the “green revolution” – or the BG varieties in local parlance – are out of place in some of the ecological situations in Sri Lanka. One such area is the ill-drained belt of about 28,350 ha stretching from Negombo to midway between Matara and Tangalla, where lagoon and river basin systems of rice cultivation prevail (see map). At the mouth of the rivers and lagoons are sandbars. During the rainy season, water builds up behind the sandbars, spreads inland, and inundates the paddy fields. Floodwaters hinder cultivation until the force of the banded waters bursts the sandbars, or until the water is pumped out. These bog soils are usually less than 1 ft below sea level. Flooding and salinity prevent cultivation of the BG varieties; only traditional types

BG 78, a new rice variety developed at the Bombuwela Research Station in Sri Lanka, is suited to ill-drained soil conditions.

such as Dewareddisi and Pokkali can survive.

Even in higher reaches without continuous flooding and salinity, BG varieties have given disappointing results because of ill-drained conditions due to a surface water table and because of toxic iron deposits. During the rains, iron oxide is washed down from the surrounding red-yellow podzolic highland soils and is converted into the reduced toxic form under the ill-drained conditions. The only way to increase yields without expensive flood-control and drainage schemes is to develop more hardy varieties.

Such a variety, Bombuwela 78 or BW 78, was recently developed and released by research officers at the Bombuwela Research Station near Kalutara. BW 78 is now recommended for cultivation in the half-bogs and mineral soils found above the flood-stricken bog soils. BW 78 is also recommended for the better drained soils of the Colombo district (see map) where it might replace BG II-II in areas where the water supply is unstable and

where part-time cultivators cannot give their crops high levels of management.

Paul Peiris, who bred BW 78, described it as “a rugged, rustic, rice. Not only is it resistant to poor drainage and iron toxicity, but it also shows a fair degree of field resistance to the brown planthopper, gall midge, and the leaf-rolling caterpillar, and to the paddy bug, which is the most serious pest in this region.”

The paddy bug is probably discouraged from damaging the earheads because of the tough seed coat, which also discourages the paddy moth from destroying stored grain. BW 78 is also tolerant of blast and bacterial blight diseases. Its height (90 cm) and spreading growth habit permits a certain degree of flooding while discouraging excessive weed growth.

BW 78 is a 4-month variety with a white, round, samba-like grain. It is derived from a cross between H 501 (Podiwi a-8 H 5) and Selection 306, and can be cultivated both in *maha* and *yala* seasons.

A few experimental seed kits were issued to extension officers for demonstration purposes this *yala* season in Colombo, Galle, Kalutara, Matara, and Ratnapura districts. Production kits and larger stocks of seed paddy are expected to be ready for release next *maha* season.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Toward rice varieties with multiple resistance

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Outbreaks of brown planthoppers, grassy stunt, blast, and sheath blight on popular high yielding varieties (HYV) grown in Kerala have emphasized the importance of an alert and aggressive rice breeding program. The earlier concept in rice breeding was to produce rice varieties

adapted to a particular stress condition. Consequently, varieties that were developed have built-in resistance to a single pest or disease, but have no multiple resistance to withstand varied stress conditions under which the crop is grown. To develop varieties with multiple resistance, the hybridization program at the Rice Research Station, Pattambi, was expanded. Forty-five cultures (see table) recorded resistance to one or more pests and diseases together. Most donors responsible for the resistance were IRRI lines.

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